

Precipitation of Thorium as Thorium Sebacate from Homogeneous Solution

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Manuscript received 25 June 1973 ; accepted 23 May 1974

Quantitative precipitation of thorium sebacate has been carried out, employing PFHS method, by *in situ* generation of sebacic acid by the hydrolysis of methyl ester of sebacic acid. The precipitate is coarse, non adhering and easy to filter.

PRECIPITATION of metal chelates from homogeneous solution (PFHS) is now a well established technique in gravimetric methods. By this technique the precipitant is not added directly in the customary manner but is slowly generated by a chemical reaction within the solution. The precipitate is formed by a homogeneous process which eliminates the undesirable concentration effects as is the case with the conventional precipitation process. The precipitate formed in this manner has a more definite composition, and is dense and readily filterable.

Gorden¹ *et al* have reviewed the uses of this method and the difficulties encountered in developing such a method. In this paper the author describes a method for the precipitation of thorium sebacate from homogeneous solution using methyl ester of sebacic acid.

Experimental :

Sebacic acid was prepared according to literature method². And the methyl ester of sebacic acid can be synthesized directly by esterification of sebacic acid with methanol in presence of a little hydrochloric gas. A 3% (W/V) methanol solution of the reagent was employed for the precipitation studies.

Stock solution of thorium was prepared by dissolving 3g of AR thorium nitrate ($\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in 10% HCl. The concentration of thorium in the resulting solution was determined by precipitating as thorium sebacate $\text{Th}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{CO}_2)_2$ and subsequent ignition to thoria,

Standard solutions of diverse ions, viz. Ce(III), Al(III) and Fe(III), were prepared from AR reagents.

Procedure

Thorium solution (25ml) is taken in a 500ml beaker and diluted to 100 l. To this solution 100ml of methyl ester of sebacic acid were added and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 3 hrs, when a coarse, nonadhering precipitate is separated out. The precipitate has no tendency to stick to glass and was more easily filterable as compared to that obtained by conventional method. The precipitate is filtered through a filter crucible, washed thoroughly with hot water followed by methanol (25ml). It is finally dried at 110° and weighed.

In another set of determination, the filtration was carried using ashless filter paper and the precipitate was ignited in a muffle furnace at 750°–800° to constant weight. Determinations were also carried from solution containing diverse metal ions and the results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF THORIUM BY PFHS AND CONVENTIONAL METHODS ALONE OR IN THE PRESENCE OF DIVERSE METAL IONS.

Thorium taken in mg.	Thorium found in mg.			
	PFHS Method		Conventional Method	
	at 100°.	at 80°.	at 110°.	at 80°.
Without Diverse Metal Ions				
25.03	24.98	25.01	25.11	25.00
50.06	50.01	50.08	50.22	50.10
75.09	75.11	75.14	75.18	75.05
100.12	100.12	100.11	100.21	100.17
Along with diverse Metal Ions (added, Ce III 20 mg.)				
75.09	75.01	75.08	—	74.78
Added Fe (III) 20 mg.				
50.06	50.02	50.05	—	50.17
Added Al (III) 20 mg.				
75.09	75.06	75.08	—	75.24

Although quantitative separation of thorium takes place both in the conventional and PFHS methods, the precipitate obtained in PFHS method is easy to filter and has a definite composition, the precipitate can be dried at a low temperature and weighed as such, unlike the conventional method.

References

1. L. GORDEN, N. Habeiman, O. E. Hilman, (Jr.) and P. Ellefsen; cited in Analytical Chemistry, edited by Philip W. West, A.M.G. Macdonald and T. S. West. (Elsevier Publishing Co., Amsterdam), 1963, 150.
2. O. N. WITT., *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 220.